

Creation of a Functional Vegan Sausage Dry Mix Using Plant-Based Ingredients: A Comparative Study on Proximate, Microbial, Shelf Life, and Sensory Attributes

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ABSTRACT:

This research explores the development of a vegan sausage dry mix, underscoring its potential as a sustainable source of plant-based protein. The formulation integrates protein-rich ingredients, specifically soya chunks and white beans, to create a complete amino acid profile that supports optimal health. The study evaluates several parameters, including proximate composition (moisture, protein, fat, ash, and carbohydrate content), microbiological quality (total plate count and yeast/mold count), shelf-life stability (accelerated shelf-life testing), gluten content, and sensory characteristics assessed by a semi-trained panel list. Three formulations were prepared: control sample S0, experimental samples S1 (35:15 ratio of soya chunks to rice flour), and S2 (30:20 ratio). Findings revealed that sample S2 exhibited significantly higher protein and carbohydrate levels compared to both control sample S0 and sample S1, along with lower moisture content. Microbiological analysis indicated sample S2 had reduced microbial counts relative to the control samples. Shelf-life studies demonstrated that the dry mix remained stable over six days, with projections indicating a potential shelf life of up to four months without significant quality changes. Sensory evaluation showed that sample S2 was favourably received in terms of flavor, appearance, and overall acceptance compared to the control formulations. Therefore, sample S2 is recommended for further development as a promising vegan sausage alternative.

Keywords: Dry Mix, Microbiological analysis, Proximate analysis, Rice flour, Sensory evaluation, Shelf life, Soya chunks, Vegan sausage.

INTRODUCTION:

The increasing demand for plant-based alternatives has led to a significant rise in the production of vegetarian and vegan sausages, which are crafted from a diverse array of plant-based ingredients such as soy protein, tofu, nuts, beets, and

various vegetable proteins. These ingredients not only provide essential nutrients but also serve to reduce reliance on animal-derived fats¹, numerous strategies have been proposed to lower the content of animal fats and improve the lipid profiles of these products, thereby promoting healthier dietary choices. Vegan sausages present a viable alternative to traditional meat products when formulated correctly to achieve comparable texture and flavor. This shift contributes to decreasing meat consumption and positioning plant-based sausages as promising and sustainable². This tendency has been further accelerated by the growing numbers of flexitarians and vegans and by increased awareness of the benefits of meat alternatives over traditional meat products. Moreover, significant spending from the food industry and government funding for research and development are important factors propelling the quick development of plant-based meat alternatives³. It is well recognized that plant-based meat substitutes are very nutritious and provide essential amino acids, vitamins, minerals, fiber, and few calories. Health experts are already investigating substitute ingredients including soy, peas, beets, and mushrooms to improve the nutritional value of sausages made from plant materials. Studies reveal that these alternatives may imitate the flavor, texture, look, and nutritional value of particular meats rather well⁴. Plant-based meat substitutes are becoming increasingly popular as people grow more conscious of environmental and health issues. An innovative method to reduce animal consumption and promote ecologically sustainable growth was employed in another study to manufacture vegan sausages using grape seed flour⁵. Reduced cholesterol, higher fibre content, and a decreased risk of heart disease are just a few of the health advantages that make grape seed flour a viable substitute for those with dietary limitations, such as those with coeliac disease. Food scientists are now investigating plant-based components that mimic the flavor and texture of meat while improving nutritional profiles, such as soy, lentils, beans, and peas. Because they include necessary amino acids and high protein content, soybeans are among the most significant plant-based protein sources⁶.

In addition, dry mixes for vegan sausages present distinct advantages over pre-made options, particularly regarding shelf life. Their lower moisture content not only reduces food waste but also facilitates better storage solutions. Drying is an ancient yet effective method of food preservation that minimizes water activity, thereby inhibiting microbial contamination⁷. This process is especially beneficial for individuals seeking quick and convenient meal options without compromising nutrition or safety. By optimizing formulations and employing appropriate drying techniques—such as spray drying, tray drying, freeze drying, or vacuum drying—manufacturers can create shelf-stable dry mix powders suitable for various culinary applications.

Rising Prevalence of Gluten Sensitivity:

Gluten is the most capacity protein of wheat grains. Gluten may be a complex blend of hundreds of related but particular proteins, basically gliadin and glutenin. Comparable storage proteins exist as secalin in the rye, hordein in grain, and avenins in oats and are collectively alluded to as “gluten”⁸. The proline-rich residues make tight and compact structures that can intervene in the antagonistic safe responses in coeliac illness. Celiac infection, gluten sensitivity, or gluten-affectability is caused due to glutamine protein from grains like wheat, rye, and grain (collectively called gluten). This protein harms the little digestive tract and causes stomach torment, bloating, shortcoming, etc. Celiac malady, gluten hypersensitivity, or gluten affectability has never truly taken in creating nations like India. In any case, in countries like the UK, USA, Canada, and other parts of Europe, gluten-free nourishment has become very prevalent. With a predominance rate of almost one in 100 -133 individuals around the world, celiac illness is far-reaching all over the globe, and lifelong utilization of gluten-free nourishment is prescribed treatment for this sensitivity. Apart from celiac illness patients, gluten-free nourishments are moreover expended by wellbeing cognizant individuals for weight administration and high protein diet and by patients with diabetes, autism, and nourishment hypersensitivities⁹. The worldwide incidence of this illness has expanded by a normal of 7.5% percent per year, fulfilling the nourishment industry to create gluten-free diets¹⁰.

Celiac disease, an autoimmune disorder triggered by gluten consumption, affects approximately 1 in 140 individuals worldwide. This condition leads to significant intestinal damage when gluten is ingested; however, removing gluten from the diet allows the immune system to initiate healing and prevent further damage. Historically, celiac disease was considered rare in India, but recent studies indicate that its prevalence has risen to about 0.6%, particularly in northern regions where wheat is a staple food (Celiac India). This research aims to formulate, develop, and evaluate the nutritional and sensory attributes of a vegan sausage dry mix while assessing its shelf life⁹.

Flowchart 1. Preparation of vegan sausage mix

Materials and Method:

Procurement of Raw Ingredients:

Ingredients like Texturized vegetable protein, rice flour, jackfruit seed powder, almond flour, coconut flour, white bean powder, onion powder, bell pepper powder, garlic powder, cumin, fennel, black pepper, salt, coriander seed powder, Italian seasonings, smoked paprika were procured from local market Chennai.

Development of Vegan Sausage Dry Mix Product:

Preparation of Powder

The powder preparation involved several key steps to ensure the quality and consistency of the ingredients used in the vegan sausage dry mix. The soya chunks and white beans were soaked in water overnight to improve their texture and make processing simpler. The onion, garlic, and bell pepper (capsicum) were cut into uniform pieces. Almonds were also sliced. The sliced veggies and almonds were uniformly distributed on trays and placed in a tray dryer set to 60°C for four to six hours. This drying procedure aims to remove moisture from the food while keeping its flavor and nutritional content. The soy chunks, white

beans, almonds, and vegetables were individually dried and processed to a fine flour consistency using a food processor. The powdered samples were sieved to eliminate lumps and dust particles, leaving a smooth texture. It is then weighed using precision weighing equipment that properly follows the formula. The weighted materials were thoroughly combined to ensure an even distribution of nutrients throughout the dry mix. They were stored at room temperature in low-density polyethylene (LDPE) sachets to keep the powders fresh and prevent moisture absorption.

Table1. Development of vegan sausage dry mix

Sample	Ratio
Sample 1 (S1)	35:15 (soya chunks: rice flour)
Sample 2 (S2)	30:20 (soya chunks: rice flour)

Manufacturing of vegan sausage:

Method 1

Several procedures are included in the development process to create the vegan sausage with the greatest texture and flavor. The dry sausage mix was first hydrated by adding 100–150 mL of water. Since it activates the ingredients and helps the right consistency form, After good mixing, the wet substance is molded into logs manually, this step is essential for cooking the sausages uniformly. The formed logs are securely wrapped in parchment paper before being sealed with aluminum foil, they are twisted like candies. This two-layer coating prevents the sausage from drying and keeps it moist throughout cooking. After that, the wrapped sausages were steamed for 15 to 20. Steaming sausages is an excellent cooking method that keeps flavor and moisture while enabling them to firm up. After steaming, the sausages are let to rest at room temperature for 5-10 minutes. Finally, the cooked sausages over low heat for five to ten minutes, or until golden brown. This stage provides the required char and enhances flavor through caramelization, resulting in a pleasant visual and flavor profile.

Method 2:

A certain amount of water (100-150 mL) was added to the dry sausage mixture. This hydration stage is crucial for activating the components and forming a cohesive slurry of the correct consistency for further shaping. After thorough mixing, the hydrated mixture was shaped into uniform logs. Maintaining uniform size is critical for smooth cooking and consistent texture throughout the product. The created logs are then fried in oil over low heat until they reach the desired golden brown color. This frying method was chosen to enhance flavor through caramelization while also creating a crispy exterior that retains moisture within the sausage.

Nutritional Analysis:

Samples S1 and S2, together with a control sample, were utilized to assess the proximate composition of the vegan sausages using the AOAC (2000) standard techniques. Protein, carbohydrates, fats, fibre, and moisture were some of the elements that were looked at. The carbohydrate content was calculated using the difference method, which takes the total of all other components and subtracts it from 100% to get the carbohydrate percentage. The FSSAI 03.014:2023¹¹ criteria were used to calculate the gluten level of the vegan sausages. This assessment is important to determine acceptability for those with coeliac disease or gluten sensitivity.

Microbiology Analysis:

Evaluation of Total plate counts, yeast, and mold counts are done on vegan sausage samples to evaluate the microbiological safety and quality. The food samples were serially diluted with sterile saline or peptone water, and aliquots of the diluted sample were plated onto an appropriate agar substrate and allowed to incubate. To facilitate microbial development, plates were incubated for a set amount of time at specific temperatures, following incubation, colonies were enumerated to calculate the total viable microbial load, Yeast, and Mold^{12,13}.

Shelf-life study:

The shelf life of food products is important information for consumers, this sample is determined by using the ACCELERATED SHELF-LIFE TESTING (ASLT) method. Shelf-life testing is monitoring the changes in the quality depletion indicator during storage, under conditions that reasonably predict the scenario on the market shelves. However, testing procedures for shelf life assessment under accelerated storage environments can be used when quality depletion occurs rather slowly in typical storage conditions. This testing process, known as accelerated shelf-life testing (ASLT), can reduce the time required to predict product shelf life when used correctly¹⁴.

Sensory Evaluation:

Sensory evaluation is a crucial aspect of food product development, for assessing the quality and acceptability of food products, including vegan sausage. By employing a hedonic scale, panelists can quantitatively express their liking (9- like extremely) or disliking (1- dislike extremely) for various sensory attributes such as appearance, aroma, flavor, texture, and overall acceptability. These parameters provide valuable insights into consumer preferences and guide product development and improvement. By understanding consumer preferences through sensory evaluation researchers can identify areas for improvement, ensure product acceptability, and optimize formulations¹⁵. Panel Judges having good health status and interested in the sensory evaluation were selected from the Department of Food Technology, Chennai.

Statistical Analysis:

To determine the level of significance, the data was analysed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and a randomized complete block design.

Result and Discussion:

Nutritional Analysis:

sample	Moisture	Protein	Fat	Crude fibre	Total ash	Carbohydrate
S0 (Control sample)	2.85± 0.15 ^c	6.76 ±0.19 ^a	19.35± 0.14 ^d	8.33 ±0.18 ^c	7.51 ±0.04 ^b	29.51 ± 0.09 ^f
S1 (Sample 1)	2.19 ±0.02 ^a	23.45 ±0.55 ^d	8.17 ±0.22 ^c	4.21± 0.49 ^b	7.79 ± 0.04 ^c	53.75 ± 0.06 ^e
S2 (Sample 2)	2.17 ±0.10 ^a	24.41± 0.40 ^e	7.88 ±0.13 ^d	4.39 ±0.12 ^b	6.29 ±0.03 ^c	55.58 ± 0.29 ^f

Table 2: Proximate Analysis for Vegan sausage mixes sample

Note: [Control sample S0 - Eggplant wet mix, Sample S1- soya chunks: rice flour (35:15), Sample S2 – soya chunks: rice flour (30:20) ratio].

a) Moisture:

Sample S2 (2.17) exhibits a lower moisture content compared to the control sample S0 (2.85) and sample S1 (2.19), which is advantageous for extending the shelf life of the dry mix. The reduced moisture level in sample S2 contributes to its stability and longevity, making it a suitable option for storage. Soya chunks, known for their high moisture absorption, significantly increase in bulk and weight upon cooking, contrasting with vegetables that do not exhibit the same degree of expansion¹⁶. This characteristic is essential for understanding the functional properties of the ingredients used in vegan sausages. The control sample S0 contains elevated moisture levels primarily due to the inclusion of eggplant, which has a high moisture content¹⁷. Both the final product's texture and shelf life may be affected by this. The moisture content of the jackfruit seed flour used in sample S2, on the other hand, is lower, which assists in reducing the moisture levels overall¹⁸.

a) Protein:

The protein content of the vegan sausage was examined, and the findings indicate significant differences that are directly connected to the material selection. Sample S0 (6.76 g), the control sample, had a much lower protein content than samples S1 (23.45 g) and S2 (24.41 g). The primary cause of this increase is the inclusion of soy chunks, which are recognized to be a fantastic source of protein^{19,20}. As a possible supply of essential nutrients, particularly protein, soybean-based goods, such as soy chunks, are an excellent choice for the production of plant-based products¹⁵. Furthermore, although jackfruit is a component of the recipe, its meager 1.72 % of protein per sis is contributed by it.

b) Fat:

The significant variations in vegan sausage fat content can be attributed to variations in vegan sausage composition. Sample S0, the control, had 19.35 g of fat, which is significantly greater than samples S1 (8.17 g) and S2 (7.88 g). The main cause of this difference is the addition of eggplant to the control sample, which has large concentrations of unsaturated fatty acids, most notably linoleic acid²¹, and significant quantities of saturated fatty acids, namely palmitic acid. Eggplant fat improves the mouthfeel and overall sensory experience of meat analogs by adding a good texture to the product¹⁹. In contrast, samples S¹ and S² incorporate jackfruit seed flour and soya chunks, both of which are known for their lower fat content. Specifically, jackfruit seed flour has been identified as having reduced fat levels¹⁸, making it an advantageous ingredient for formulating lower-fat vegan sausages.

c) Fiber:

The control sample S⁰ exhibited a fiber concentration of 8.33 g, which is notably higher—approximately twice as much—than that found in samples S¹ (4.21 g) and S² (4.39 g). The elevated fiber levels in sample S⁰ suggest that eggplant can serve as an effective dietary source of fiber, which is critical for digestive health. The role of dietary fiber in promoting gastrointestinal

function is well-documented; it aids in the elimination of toxins and harmful substances from the digestive tract, thereby potentially reducing the risk of gastrointestinal cancers, including stomach and colon cancer²². The results reported by²³ reinforce the idea that eggplant's high fiber content may contribute to these preventive benefits, highlighting the vegetable's potential relevance in cancer prevention methods.

d) Ash:

Sample S1's ash content was 7.79 g, marginally more than control sample S0's 7.51 g. The ash content of Sample S2, however, was lower (6.29 g). These variations might be related to the different mineral compositions present in each sample, as mentioned by²⁴. Larger ash contents in samples S0 and S1 indicate increased mineral concentrations, which are critical for several physiological functions. Higher concentrations of manganese, zinc, and copper—all essential minerals—in eggplant contribute to its nutritional value and potential health benefits²³.

e) Carbohydrate:

The carbohydrate amount of the sausage samples varied significantly, notably in sample S2, which had a carbohydrate value of 55.58 g. This quantity is somewhat larger than sample S1's 53.75 g and far surpasses the carbohydrate level of control sample S0, which was just 29.51 g. These differences show the possible impact of growing circumstances, harvest maturity, and genetic variables on sausage nutrition. The increased carbohydrate content of samples S2 and S1 suggests that they might be more important sources of energy than sample S0. Because these samples have higher carbohydrate levels, they could be especially appealing to people who want to increase their intake of complex carbohydrates²⁵, which are important for overall health and long-term energy release. Numerous biomolecules, including lipids, polysaccharides, and carbohydrates, may exist, according to the study's additional absorption bands¹⁶. Samples S2 and S1 have more carbohydrates than other samples, which provides more energy and may confer additional health benefits associated with polysaccharides. Weight control strategies may benefit from these substances as they improve digestion and boost satiety.

Figure 1. Proximate Analysis of sausage samples

Microbiological Analysis:

Table 3: Microbiological examination of vegan banger mix

Sample	Total plate count (CFU/g)	Yeast and Mold count (CFU/g)
S ⁰ (control sample)	700	800
S ¹ (sample 1)	34×10^{-4}	9×10^{-3}
S ² (sample 2)	9×10^{-4}	4×10^{-3}

To evaluate the safety and effectiveness of microbiological methods, the total plate count (TPC) and yeast and mold count (YMC) were calculated for every sausage sample. The TPC findings showed that the control sample S0 had 700 CFU/g. Samples S1 and S2 had TPC values of 34×10^{-4} and 9×10^{-4} CFU/ml, respectively. The data indicate that samples S1 and S2 were within consumable limits, while the microbiological quality of the control sample was greater when compared to control. The YMC results further demonstrated that the control sample S0 was within the allowable range of 800 CFU/g. Sample S1 exhibited a YMC of 9×10^{-3} CFU/ml, while sample S2 had a YMC of 4×10^{-3} CFU/ml. Although every sample was confirmed to be below safe consumption limits, these results imply that there might be a discernible variance in the yeast and mold present among the samples. The lower values for sample S2 compared to sample S1 would indicate better handling or preservation techniques.

Gluten Analysis:

Table 4.
Vegan Sausage sample (30:20) flour

Sample	Unit
S ² (Sample 2)	<0.1 %

Gluten Analysis of Mix Sample S²-Soya Chunks :Rice

The gluten content in the dry mix was evaluated, revealing a concentration of less than 0.1%. This analysis was conducted exclusively on the acceptable sample S², which indicates its suitability for individuals with gluten sensitivities or celiac disease.

Shelf-Life Analysis:

The shelf life of food products is important information for consumers, this sample is determined by using the ACCELERATED SHELF-LIFE TESTING (ASLT) method. Accelerated shelf-life testing (ASLT) aims to accelerate the rate of deterioration of the product without altering the mechanisms or order of changes seen in the product under normal storage conditions. The product was tested daily it was observed every day for the microbial count to find out any spoilage. Finally, after 6 days of testing in the incubation of the sample is safe and can be consumed for 4 months from the date of manufacture.

Sensory Evaluation:

Mean scores for sensory attributes of a dry mix of vegan sausage are presented in Table 5. The score of sample S¹ and sample S² was 8.5 for the taste attribute. The texture of the sample was to be better in sample S² than in control sample S⁰ and sample S¹. The appearance of control sample S⁰ and sample S² was better than sample S¹. The flavor of sample S² is more compared to control sample S⁰ and sample S¹. sample S² has a high score for color compared to sample S¹ and control sample S⁰. Therefore, overall acceptability the sample S² was highly accepted.

Table 5. Sensory Analysis of the vegan sausage mix [S⁰ - control sample, S¹- sample 1 and S² - sample 2]

Sample	Appearance	Texture	Color	Taste	Flavor	Overall acceptability
S ⁰ Control Sample	8.03±0.45 ^a	7.96±0.05 ^a	8.1±0.4 ^a	7.83±0.49 ^a	8.53±0.47 ^a	8.08±0.06 ^a
S ¹ Sample 1	7.9±0.36 ^a	7.67±0.56 ^a	8.2±0.528 ^a	8.5±0.5 ^a	8.4±0.45 ^a	8.12±0.14 ^a
S ² Sample 2	8.76±0.25 ^a	8.43±0.51 ^a	8.63±0.60 ^a	8.5±0.50 ^a	8.60±0.40 ^a	8.43±0.12 ^a

Figure 2. vegan sausage samples

Figure 3. Sensory evaluation by Hedonic scale

Conclusion:

The vegan sausage dry mix developed in this study offers a promising alternative for individuals following a vegan diet. Its formulation successfully replicates the sensory attributes of traditional meat sausages, Sample S², in particular, demonstrated superior nutritional benefits and higher sensory acceptance compared to the control samples, highlighting its potential as a viable product in the expanding plant-based food market. Future research should explore additional ingredient combinations and processing methods to further enhance the vegan sausage mix's sensory qualities and nutritional profile.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest to declare.

Reference:

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